

FATIGUE PROPAGATION OF A BRIDGED CRACK IN FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

P. Levasseur , P. Paulmier , J.F. Maire , and J.L. Chaboche

*Department of Mechanics, Office National d'Etudes et de recherche Aeronautique
29 Ave de la Division Leclerc, 92322 Châtillon, France*

SUMMARY: A model for fatigue crack propagation with bridged fibers has been developed. It is based on linear fracture Mechanics combined to determination of the closure pressure exerted by the fibers, that reduces substantially the matrix crack growth. Two scales have been modeled to obtain the bridging effect expression. At the lower scale, pertinent interfacial properties have been described such as debonding and friction. Furthermore, an application is proposed from a fatigue test on SiC/Ti. It has been performed on a center-notched specimen from which the crack growth has been accurately calculated. The abilities of this model are in agreement with the different experimental stages. It offers promising prospects to find optimal interfacial properties and to establish a propagation law for bridged cracks.

KEYWORDS: fatigue propagation, bridged crack, multi-scale model, interface, debonding, friction, fiber-reinforced composite.

INTRODUCTION

Under low longitudinal loads, fatigue cracks propagate through CMM's composites, perpendicularly to the fibers. The initiation comes from initial flaws: for instance brittle reaction product at the interface, or an early fiber rupture [1-3]. This damage does not involve a catastrophic failure even if its size is the same as the structural material. Most fibers bridge the matrix cracks, which can allow a stable crack growth. In order to answer at the issue of the tolerance damage for aerospace applications, a first point to overcome is the determination of the crack propagation law for these composites.

The enhancement of fracture toughness by bridging fibers depends strongly on interfacial properties. During fatigue tests, three different behaviors have been met [4,5]. With a high interfacial strength, the propagation is followed by fiber rupture at the crack tip, excluding any bridging participation. With weak interfaces, important debonding lengths comes from the deflection of the crack. This bifurcated direction of damage, perpendicular to the matrix crack, reduces the mechanical resistance of the composite. For intermediate interfacial properties, short debonding lengths are created and the fiber bridging is more efficient to stabilize the crack growth. Only the last case is considered in this paper.

The mechanical behavior of the fiber bridging is non-linear. Dissipation occurs at the interface such as debonding and friction [6,7]. Furthermore, residual stresses, which are important in CMM's, induce anelastic strain and act directly on interfacial friction. Due to mechanical

force of bridging fibers, the Paris law, that governs the matrix crack growth, fails to model the crack propagation. A convenient way to modify it is to diminish the amplitude of the stress intensity factor (SIF) ΔK_{tip} by ΔK_b . This last term represents the influence of the fiber bridging pressure, translated at the crack tip.

The determination of the macroscopic relation which links ΔK_b to observable parameters requires a width range of experimental results and the procedure must be repeated for each material. Another approach consists in describing the force of each bridging fiber. An important relation to solve the problem is to express the relation between the pressure sustained by the bridged fibers and the crack opening displacement: $P(\delta)$. Phenomenological expressions [8] or micromechanical models with a constant friction stress have been proposed [9,10].

In this paper, the last approach is followed to model the propagation of a bridged crack and a cell model is developed to describe the $P(\delta)$ relation. Attention has been paid to take interfacial behavior into account. In a second part, fatigue tests have been performed on a SiC/Ti composite and an application of this model is proposed.

MECHANICAL MODEL

General description

This model is written in the frame of the Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics. The composite is treated as a homogenous elastic medium where a matrix crack is propagating in mode I. Matrix plasticity is not considered and the plastic zone at the crack tip is supposed to remain small.

A modified Paris' law governs the crack growth:

$$\frac{\partial a}{\partial n} = c \left(\Delta K_{tip} - K_s \right)^n \quad (1)$$

where ΔK_{tip} is the effective amplitude at the crack tip caused by combination of the external loading and the axial bridging stresses. The constants c , n and the threshold K_s depend only on matrix properties.

To model the mechanical contribution of the bridging fibers on ΔK_{tip} , two scales are used: the first one: the crack scale, at the level of the specimen and the second one: the micro scale, at the level of the constituents: fibre, matrix and interface (see Fig 1):

Fig. 1: Representation of the two scales.(a) crack scale (b) micro scale

Crack scale

The discrete fiber stresses applying on the crack surfaces, are replaced by a continuous distribution of pressure $P(x)$. This approximation is valid as long as the fibers exhibit a periodic location and their spacing distance is small compared to the crack length. By the principle of linear superposition, the neat force on the crack surfaces is $\sigma_{crack}(x) = \sigma_a - P(x)$ where σ_a is the external stress and x locates the position on the crack (see Fig 1a). P is counted negative when it tends to close the crack and positive for the opposite case. The Stress Intensity Factor can be expressed by $K = \int_0^a h(x, a, w) \cdot \sigma_{crack}(x) dx$ where $h(x, a, w)$ is the weight function [11]. Therefore, ΔK_{tip} takes the following expression:

$$\Delta K_{tip} = \Delta K_a - \Delta K_b \quad (1)$$

$$\text{with } \Delta K_a = \Delta \sigma_a \cdot F(a, w) \quad (2a)$$

$$\text{and } \Delta K_b = \int_0^a h(x, a, w) \cdot \Delta P(x) dx \quad (2b)$$

Furthermore, the crack opening displacement (COD) can be expressed according to Rice's relation [12]:

$$\delta(x) = \frac{1}{E^*} \int_x^a h(x, s, w) \cdot \left\{ \int_0^s h(t, s, w) (\sigma_a - P(x)) dt \right\} ds \quad (3)$$

where E^* is homogenous at a Young modulus. It depends on the anisotropy of the material.

Micro scale

At the micro scale, an elementary cell is used to describe the behavior of a bridging element surrounded by matrix (see Fig 1b). It provides a relation between the continuous pressure $P(x)$, introduced at the crack level, and the crack opening displacement $\delta(x)$. The force balance over a cell section requires that an axial stress of $T(x) = \frac{P(x)}{f}$ is exerting on the bridging fiber at the crack plan. The COD results from the fiber/matrix sliding at the interface. Two relevant

features: the residual stresses and the interfacial behavior, are taken into account to obtain the response $P(\delta)$ of the bridging element.

The residual stresses are expected to be only generated by the thermal mismatch between the fibre and the matrix during the manufacturing process. They are evaluated thanks to an elastic calculation under generalized plane strains. The interface is supposed to be in compression after this process, that means we only consider composites for which the matrix expansion coefficient is greater than the fibre one.

The interfacial behavior is described by considering the propagation of a debonding zone which friction occurs in. Debonding is expressed under pure shear mode with an ONERA's model. It has been developed from Tvergaard's analysis [13] and further details are available in Ref. [14,15]. A damage variable, λ , is introduced to describe continuously the interfacial debonding from a sound state ($\lambda=0$) to a broken one ($\lambda=1$). It is controlled by jump displacements at the interface. In the present case, it depends only on the tangential displacement or sliding displacement U_t : $\lambda = 1 - \left\langle 1 - \frac{U_t}{\delta_t} \right\rangle$ where δ_t is the sliding displacement

which leads to rupture. During the evolution of λ , the shear resistance of the bond reaches a maximal level τ_{\max} before to go down to the friction level. It is expressed by a cubic function as shown in Fig. 2:

Fig 2. Interfacial behavior

The fracture energy G_{II} is represented by the dark area under the curve. A relation exists between G_{II} , τ_{\max} and δ_t : $G_{II} = \frac{9}{16} \tau_{\max} \delta_t$. Only two parameters (τ_{\max} , δ_t) or (G_{II} , δ_t) characterize the debonding model.

After complete debonding, friction is taking place as long as the two surfaces stay in contact. It is modeled using the Coulomb's law : $\tau_i = \pm \mu \langle -\sigma_r \rangle$. The normal stress, σ_r , depends on the residual radial stress and the Poisson's contraction effect which is not usually negligible [16]. Analytical solution of $P(\delta)$ are obtained from the micromechanical analysis developed by [17]. It is based on the determination of the axial fiber stress σ_f and its integral along the debonding zone which is proportional to the COD. A key relation is the load transfer of σ_f due to interfacial shear stress:

$$\frac{d\sigma_f}{dz} = \pm \frac{2\tau_i}{r_f} \quad (4)$$

where z is the interface abscise and r_f the fiber radius. The determination of τ_i leads to solve the whole problem. It depends on interfacial behavior and history through the loading sequences: monotonic loading or unloading/reloading sequences. During the loading, the debonding length, l_d , is extending and τ_i is given by the debonding model coupled with friction. During cyclic sequences, a reverse slip, l_r , is growing from the crack plan where the direction of sliding becomes opposite. This implies a sign change of τ_i [10]. A notable feature of this analytical solution is that the stress field at the debonding tip is completely described (see Fig. 3b) and no jumping stress is introduced as it is usually proposed in micromechanical models [10].

Fig. 3. Response of the bridging cell.

(a) Relation $P(\delta)$ (b). Shear stress repartition along the interface

The response $P(\delta)$ of the cell is plotted in Fig 3a. for a SiC/Ti cell. The initial opening when $P=0$ is due to the presence of residual stresses which tend to open the crack because the matrix is initially in tension. For the loading sequence, both G_{II} and μ influence the shape of the curve. For a cyclic sequence, friction causes a hysteresis loop characteristic of an energy dissipation. It affects the response as long as the reverse slip, l_r , is lower than the debond length, l_d . When l_r reaches l_d an elastic behavior takes place. In the remaining sections, the relation $P(\delta)$ will be designed by:

$$\delta(x) = \mathfrak{R}_{micro}(P(x)) \quad (5)$$

where the function \mathfrak{R}_{micro} depends on interface parameters (G_{II} , μ , δ_i) and constituent properties.

Determination of the crack growth rate

The equality between the expressions of the COD at the two scales (Eqn 3 and Eqn 5) provides the equation verified by the bridging pressure $P(x)$:

$$\mathfrak{R}_{micro}(P(x)) = \frac{1}{E^*} \int_x^a h(x, s, w) \left\{ \int_0^s h(t, s, w) (\sigma_a - P(x)) dt \right\} ds \quad (6)$$

The resolution of Eqn. 6, at any stage of the loading allows to calculate $P(x)$ along the matrix crack and to deduce $\Delta P(x)$ for a half cycle. Therefore ΔK_b and ΔK_{tip} can be calculated with Eqn 2a and Eqn 2. Eventually, the crack growth rate is determined by the Eqn 1.

As the number of cycles is high, we have preferred to use an incremental form on the crack length rather than on the number of cycles. For a given crack length a , the equation 6 is solved twice to determine $\Delta P(x)$, a first time when $\sigma_a = \sigma_{max}$, a second one when $\sigma_a = \sigma_{min}$ and the crack growth rate is calculated with Eqn 1. The procedure is repeated for each increment da , which signifies that a mean crack growth is calculated over a range of dN cycles. This method appeared to be correct as long as there is no appreciable time dependent effects over a period of dN on the constituent properties.

APPLICATION OF THE MODEL

Material

Fig 4. Representation of the experimental specimen

An Titanium alloy reinforced unidirectionally with SiC fiber has been tested by fatigue. The composite has been elaborated at SNECMA using hot pressing. The fibers keep the same orientation after process and their volume fraction is about 35%. The outer layer of 4.5 mm rich in carbon maintains weak properties of the composite interface, which allows interfacial debonding.

Experimental test

A center notched plate is loaded parallel to the fiber direction (see Fig 4). For an applied stress level that is sufficient, a fatigue crack is propagating through the whole width of the specimen. The recording of the cracked specimen with a camera is monitoring by a computer. Afterwards, the images are treated by image analysis software to provide an accurate measure of the crack length. The crack growth rate is calculated by an interpolation method according to the ASTM norm, in order to reduce the measure errors. The experimental crack growth rate presented in Fig.5 has been obtained for a test performed at 400° C under a ratio $R=0.1$ and a frequency of 50 Hz.

Fig.5 Crack growth experimental data and fitting curve of the model

Experimental results

The matrix crack exhibits a stable growth and spans over the whole width of specimen without causing its failure. These features are representative to a full-bridged crack where almost all the bridging fibers remain intact. The acceleration stage described by Ghonem [18] has not been attained, in the case the furthest fiber from the crack tip would be broken in the wake of the crack, which could lead to a catastrophic failure. Furthermore, another notable feature is the fracture surface after completely breaking the specimen. In our experiment, the fiber pull-out lengths are randomly spaced, that indicates there is no specific area with failure events.

Three parts depicted the crack growth curve:

- In the first one, a neat deceleration occurs; the first points are excluded due to the experimental errors at the beginning of the test. The bridging has a significant shielding effect over the driving force. At room temperature under the same loading, the crack has even been completely stopped. The increasing of temperature accelerates the crack rate which has been already mentioned [18,19]
- In the second, a steady state is reached maintaining a constant crack growth. A balance has been established between the acceleration effect due to the extension of the crack and the deceleration effect due to the bridged fibers.
- In the third one, although no fiber breaks, a slight acceleration happens when the crack reaches the edge of the specimen. This suggests that for high ΔK_a the bridging effect is less efficient.

On the other hand, at a smaller size scale, acceleration sequences and deceleration sequences follow in turn. The period of this fluctuation is about the width of the elementary cell. This indicates that the growth rate is modified when the crack is bypassing a row of fibers. Several causes may be responsible for this phenomenon : the deflection of the crack, the local fiber volume fraction, the variation of matrix residual stresses or the blunting of the crack tip.

Model results

The fitting of the experiment gives an appropriate result (see Fig 5). The trend of the crack growth is well described for each part : the initial deceleration, the steady state and the final acceleration. Furthermore, the material parameters used to describe the propagation law for the titanium matrix are in agreement with the usual values: $Ks = 2.3 \text{ Mpa m}^{1/2}$, $c = 5 \text{ e}^{-12}$ and $n = 2.48$ [1].

This model cannot describe the fluctuation at the cell size. However, at a macroscopic point of view, in order to predict the tolerance of the material, this issue appeared to be lesser important. This phenomenon is complex to model, the two scales interact each other and a more refine description is required. In that way, Xu et al have proposed a crack trapping model [20]

CONCLUSION

The bridging fibers exert significant effects on the fatigue crack propagation, reducing the growth rate in an appreciable way. Their performance depends on the behavior of the fiber/matrix interface. The main characteristics of the proposed model is to take interfacial properties in to account, especially debonding and friction. This ability is of a great interest for the design of materials. The optimal properties of interface remain a complex problem and should be overcome by this kind of model.

On the other hand, direct expressions can be deduced from the results of this two-scale model. It requires analyzing systematically the influence of the pertinent parameters. This could lead at term, to a macroscopic law for the bridged crack propagation.

Furthermore, experimental shapes with finite width and the presence of a notch can be treated. Other states than the usual state-steady have been described which allows further developments. For instance, the effects of fiber fracture could be analyzed with a statistical approach, the fiber stress state being calculated by the model. The issue is necessary to evaluate the damage tolerance of these materials; such events can lead to a catastrophic failure. Other aspects for future developments are to incorporate matrix stress relaxation, effects for high temperature and hold time effects

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors would like to thank Prof. H. Ghonem for its collaboration with our department and his valuable recommendations for the testing procedures (Professor in Mechanics of Materials Laboratory, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Rhode Island). The support os SNECMA for the specimen manufacturing and the financial support of DRET (French Ministry of Defence) are also gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Legrand, "Fatigue de composites à matrice métallique base titane à renfort unidirectionnel de fibres SiC," . Ecole Nationale des Mines de Paris, 1997.
- [2] M. Okazaki, N. Tokiya, and H. Nakatani, "Stable crack growth and damage tolerance evaluation of Ti-24Al-11Nb matrix composite unidirectionally reinforced with SiC fibers," presented at Damage and Failure of Interfaces, Vienna, 1997.
- [3] R. A. Naik and W. S. Johnson, "Observation of fatigue crack initiation and damage growth in notched titanium matrix composites," *Composite Materials: Fatigue and Fracture*, pp. 753-771, 1989.
- [4] H. Ghonem, Y. Wen, and D. Zheng, "Fatigue crack growth characteristics of Ti- β 21S neat laminates," *Applied Mechanics*, vol. 34, pp. 161-180, 1993.
- [5] H. Ghonem, "Fatigue crack growth mechanisms in Titanium Metal Matrix Composites," Air Force Office of Scientific Research AFOSR-92-F49620, 1996.
- [6] B. Guichet, "Identification de la loi de comportement interfaciale d'un composite SiC/Ti," in *Génie des matériaux*: Ecole Centrale Lyon, 1998.
- [7] D. B. Marshall, M. C. Shaw, and W. L. Morris, "Measurement of interfacial debonding and sliding resistance in fiber reinforced intermetallics," *Acta. Metall. Mater.*, vol. 40, No. 3, pp. 443-454, 1992.
- [8] T. Fett, "Influence of bridging stresses on specimen compliances," *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, vol. 53, No. 3, pp. 363-370, 1996.
- [9] R. M. McMeeking and A. G. Evans, "Matrix fatigue cracking in fiber composites," *Mechanics of Materials*, vol. 9, No. 217-227, 1990.
- [10] D. B. Marshall, B. N. Cox, and A. G. Evans, "Matrix fatigue cracking in fiber composites," *Acta. Metall.*, vol. 33, 1985.
- [11] H. Bückner, "A novel principle for the computation of stress intensity factors," *ZAMM50*, vol. 9, pp. 529-546, 1970.
- [12] J. R. Rice, "Some remarks on elastic crack tip stress fields," *Int. J. Solids Structures*, vol. 8, pp. 751-758, 1972.
- [13] V. Tvergaard, "Effect of fibre debonding in a Whisker-Reinforced Metal," *Mat. Scienc. and Eng.*, vol. A125, pp. 203-213, 1990.
- [14] J.-L. Chaboche, R. Girard, and A. Schaff, "Numerical analysis of composite systems by using interphase/interface models," *Computational Mechanics*, vol. 20, 1997.
- [15] J.-L. Chaboche, R. Girard, and P. Levasseur, "On the interface debonding models," *Int. J. Damage Mechanics*, vol. 6, 1997.

- [16] D. B. Marshall and W. C. Oliver, "An indentation method for measuring residual stresses in fiber-reinforced ceramics," *Mat. Scienc. and Eng.*, vol. A126, pp. 95-103, 1990.
- [17] J. W. Hutchinson and H. M. Jensen, "Models of fiber debonding and pull-out in brittle composites with friction," *Mechanics of Materials*, vol. 9, pp. 139-163, 1990.
- [18] H. Ghonem, "Fatigue crack growth," in *Titanium Matrix Composites*, S. Mall and T. Nicholas, Eds.: Technomic, 1998.
- [19] P. J. Cotterill and P. Bowen, "Fatigue crack growth in a fibre-reinforced Titanium MMC at ambient and elevated temperatures," *Composites*, vol. 24, No. 3, pp. 214-221, 1993.
- [20] G. Xu, A. F. Bower, and M. Ortiz, "The influence of crack trapping on the toughness of fiber reinforced composites," *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, vol. 46, No. 10, pp. 1815-1833, 1998.